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Nonlinear Optical Properties of Spirocyclohexadine Photochromes: Insights From DFT Calculations[†]

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The second-order nonlinear optical properties of 1,3-indandione-derived spirocyclohexadine compounds, a new class of photochromes showing sensitivity to both UV and visible lights, are investigated by means of density functional theory. The calculations predict that these compounds should display a large first hyperpolarizability variation upon commutation between their cyclic spiropyran and their merocyanine form. We also show that significant enhancement of the NLO response of the merocyanine form, as well as of the NLO contrast, can be achieved by means of appropriate chemical substitution, which makes these derivatives highly appealing for potential use in photo-responsive NLO devices.

1 Introduction

The design of molecular switches displaying variations in their electronic, optical, or magnetic properties in response to light irradiation has raised high interest in the last decades, owing to their potential for applications in a broad number of fields such as signal processing, information storage, chemical sensing or drug delivery.^{1,2} In this context, photochromic compounds having the ability to commute between two or more chemical forms with contrasted second-order nonlinear optical (NLO) responses are of particular interest, since the non-resonant character of these latter can be exploited to probe the electronic state of light-responsive systems without triggering uncontrolled photoconversions or photochemical side reactions.^{3–5}

Spiroheterocyclic compounds such as spiropyrans, spirooxazines or benzazolo-oxazolidines are one of the oldest class of photochromes that exhibit large NLO contrasts.^{6–10} As a common feature, this family of molecules presents a stable colorless form, in which two heterocyclic functional groups are orthogonally bound through a sp³-hybridized spiro-carbon. The photochromism is due to the electrocyclic cleavage of the spiro junction upon UV light irradiation, which produces a colorful open merocyanine (MC) form. The closed spiropyran (SP) form is recovered either by heating or exposure to visible light. Owing to its charge-transfer character mediated by electron delocalization, the MC form displays a large first hyperpolarizability, whereas the

spiro junction disrupts the electron conjugation in the SP species, giving rise to a low NLO response.

Recently, Khodorkovsky and collaborators reported the design of 1,3-indandione-derived spirocyclohexadine photochromes (Figure 1). These compounds constitute a new class of spiropyran-like derivatives which exhibit a particular behavior as conversion to the MC forms can be triggered using visible light.^{11,12} Unlike typical spiro-compounds, the MC forms are not photosensitive, discoloration occurring spontaneously in the dark with rates depending on temperature and solvent.

Fig. 1 Photochromic reaction of 1,3-indandione-derived spirocyclohexadine compounds. Representative torsional angles are displayed, as well as (in red) the π -conjugated segment considered for the calculation of the bond length alternation.

In this work, we evaluate the potential of this new family of photochromes for NLO applications. The first hyperpolarizabilities of the SP and of the (E,E) and (Z,E) MC forms of the three derivatives schematized in Figure 1, as well as their contrasts, are first computed by means of density functional theory (DFT). The NLO responses are rationalized in relation with the geometrical structure of the compounds, the nature of the electron-donating substituent R, as well as by analyzing the electronic structure of the low-lying excited states. In the light of these results, different chemical functionalization patterns are then proposed in order to

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further enhance the first hyperpolarizability of the MC forms and maximize the NLO contrast upon SP→MC isomerization.

2 Computational approach

Geometrical structures were optimized in the framework of DFT using the M06-2X exchange–correlation (XC) functional¹³ together with the 6-311G(d) basis set. Each structure was characterized as a real minimum of the potential energy surface based on its positive harmonic vibrational force constants. Linear and second-order nonlinear optical properties were computed using time-dependent (TD) DFT¹⁴ at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level. Previous investigations demonstrated that this XC functional was reliable to calculate first hyperpolarizabilities of push-pull conjugated dyes, owing to its substantial amount (54%) of long-range Hartree–Fock exchange.^{7,15–18} Frequency-dependent hyperpolarizabilities were calculated using an incident wavelength (energy) of 1907 nm (0.65 eV). Solvent effects were included in both geometry optimizations and calculations of optical responses by using the integral equation formalism of the polarized continuum model (IEF-PCM).^{19,20} Several solvents with different dielectric constants (ϵ) were considered, in line with those employed for experimental characterizations:¹¹ n-octane ($\epsilon_0 = 1.941$ in the static limit, $\epsilon_\infty = 1.953$ at infinite frequency), toluene ($\epsilon_0 = 2.374$, $\epsilon_\infty = 2.238$), chloroform ($\epsilon_0 = 4.711$, $\epsilon_\infty = 2.091$), dichloromethane ($\epsilon_0 = 8.930$, $\epsilon_\infty = 2.028$) and acetone ($\epsilon_0 = 20.493$, $\epsilon_\infty = 1.846$). All calculations were performed using the Gaussian16 package.²¹

The reported NLO quantities are related to hyper-Rayleigh scattering (HRS) experiments. For a non-polarized incident light of frequency ω , the intensity of the vertically polarized (parallel to the Z axis of the laboratory frame) SHG signal, scattered at 90° with respect to the propagation direction (parallel to the Y axis), is proportional to the square of the HRS hyperpolarizability:

$$\beta_{HRS}(-2\omega; \omega, \omega) = \sqrt{\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle + \langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle} = \sqrt{\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle} \left(1 + \frac{1}{DR}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle$ and $\langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle$ are ensemble averages arising from the isotropic distribution of molecular orientations in dilute solutions. The expressions of these latter in terms of molecular β tensor components are provided in Ref. 22. The depolarization ratio (DR in equation 1) is the ratio between the scattered HRS intensities obtained when the incident light is vertically ($\langle \beta_{ZZZ}^2 \rangle$) and horizontally ($\langle \beta_{ZXX}^2 \rangle$) polarized. This ratio provides information on the geometry of the molecular part responsible for the second harmonic light generation, and ranges between 1.5 for pure octupolar compounds and 9 for pure dipolar ones. In the case of "one-dimensional" (1D) systems for which the hyperpolarizability tensor reduces to a single diagonal component, DR is equal to 5.

The magnitude of the HRS hyperpolarizabilities of the MC forms is qualitatively rationalized using the two-state approximation, assuming that the S_1 electronic excited state is the only contributing to the sum-over-state expansion of the second-order NLO response:²³

$$\beta_{HRS} \propto \frac{\mu_{01}^2 \Delta\mu_{01}}{\Delta E_{01}^2} = \frac{3}{2} \frac{f_{01} \Delta\mu_{01}}{\Delta E_{01}^3} \quad (2)$$

where ΔE_{01} is the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ excitation energy, μ_{01} is the associated transition dipole, $f_{01} = \frac{2}{3} \Delta E_{01} \mu_{01}^2$ is the oscillator strength, and $\Delta\mu_{01} = \|\vec{\mu}_{S_1} - \vec{\mu}_{S_0}\|$ is the change in permanent dipole moment between the two electronic states. All reported β values are given in atomic units (1 a.u. of $\beta = 3.6310^{-42} \text{ m}^4 \text{V}^{-1} = 3.2063 \times 10^{-53} \text{ C}^3 \text{m}^3 \text{J}^{-2} = 8.641 \times 10^{-33} \text{ esu}$) and assume that the molecular induced dipoles are written as Taylor series of the external electric fields (T convention).²⁴

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Molecular structures and thermodynamic properties

Table 1 gathers representative structural parameters of MC isomers calculated for solvents having the lowest (n-octane) and highest (acetone) polarity (data obtained for other solvents are provided in Tables S1-S5, Electronic Supporting Information, ESI). Relative Gibbs free energies computed using standard conditions (T = 298.15 K, P = 1 atm) are also reported. In agreement with experimental populations measured in solutions left in the dark for several hours,¹¹ the initial cyclic forms are found more stable than the extended merocyanines, whatever the nature of the R substituent or solvent polarity. Moreover, the (Z,E) MC conformers are more stable than the (E,E) conformers by about 1 kcal/mol. Note that using XC functionals with a lower amount of exact exchange such as PBE0 or B3LYP leads to the reverse conclusion that MC forms are more stable than SP forms (Table S6), which validates *a posteriori* the choice of M06-2X for geometry optimizations. This is further supported by the good agreement between the obtained DFT equilibrium geometry of the SPa form and reported X-ray diffraction data (see SI).

Table 1 Bond length alternation (BLA, Å) and dihedral angles (θ , °) of the MC forms, as well as relative Gibbs free energies with respect to the SP forms (ΔG^\ominus , kcal/mol), as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311G(d) in n-octane and acetone.

	BLA	θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	ΔG^\ominus
n-octane					
2a	0.074	21.0	36.6	0.5	6.85
3a	0.071	21.9	27.7	175.7	5.63
2b	0.074	21.1	36.6	0.5	6.63
3b	0.070	21.8	27.7	175.8	5.76
2c	0.088	19.6	38.3	0.0	8.58
3c	0.085	20.5	29.7	175.4	7.56
acetone					
2a	0.063	23.2	34.6	0.0	6.43
3a	0.058	24.5	25.3	175.9	5.34
2b	0.062	23.3	34.7	0.0	6.63
3b	0.057	24.4	25.4	176.0	5.76
2c	0.083	21.2	37.5	-0.4	8.58
3c	0.080	22.3	28.6	175.4	7.56

Comparing first the (E,E) conformers of the three compounds (**2a-2c**), substituting the dimethyl-amino by a diethyl-amino group in R position does not introduce significant changes in the molecular geometry, neither in the torsion angles nor in the bond length alternation (BLA) along the conjugated linker that connects the electron-donating and electron-accepting moieties (red segment in Figure 1). On the contrary, introducing a methoxy substituent in R significantly increases the BLA, as a consequence of its lower electron-donating character. Whatever the nature of

the R substituent, the (*E,E*) to (*Z,E*) isomerization (**2**→**3**) induces a decrease of the dihedral angle θ_2 by about 9° , which enhances the π -electron conjugation between the donor and acceptor parts, as indicated by the slight lowering of the BLA. Increasing the solvent polarity also increases significantly the electron delocalization within the MC forms, which translates into a diminution of the HOMO-LUMO gap (Tables S7-S11).

3.2 Linear optical properties

The UV/vis absorption spectra calculated at the IEF-PCM:M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in n-octane and acetone for the SP and MC forms of compound **a** are displayed in Figure 2. The numerical values of vertical transition energies and oscillator strengths associated to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, calculated in n-octane and acetone, are gathered in Table 2. Complementary data are collected in ESI (Tables S7-S11 and Figure S3).

Fig. 2 UV/vis absorption spectra of the three forms of compound **a** calculated at the IEF-PCM:M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in n-octane (dashed line) and acetone (plain line).

The TD-DFT calculations nicely reproduce the qualitative features of the experimental UV/vis spectra.¹¹ Considering the **1a**→**2a** photoisomerization in n-octane, the red-shift measured experimentally from about 275 nm to 600 nm is well reproduced by our calculations, for which the maximum absorption band originally centered at 250 nm reduces in intensity while new bands characteristic of the MC form appear in the visible range (~ 500 nm), owing to the extension of π -electron conjugation induced by the ring opening. The *Z/E* isomerization from **2a** to **3a** has no impact on the position of the bands, but reduces the absorption efficiency in the 300-400 nm region while it boosts the intensity of the band corresponding to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition at 500 nm, as also revealed by the $\sim 60\%$ increase of the associated oscillator strength (Table 2). Also in agreement with experiments performed in n-octane and methylethyl ketone that report a 62 nm redshift, increasing the solvent polarity from n-octane to acetone induces a bathochromic shift of 0.3 eV of the lowest-energy absorption band. The UV/vis spectrum of compound **3b** does not differ significantly from that of **3a** (Figure S3). On the contrary, replacing the dimethyl-amino group in **3a** by a weaker methoxy donor in **3c** strongly blue shifts (by 0.26 eV in n-octane and 0.38

Table 2 Vertical transition energy (ΔE_{01} , eV) and wavelength (λ_{01} , nm), oscillator strength (f_{01} , dimensionless), charge transfer (Δq , |e|), charge transfer distance (Δr , Å), and dipole moment variation ($\Delta\mu_{01}$, D) associated to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition, as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311G(d) in n-octane and acetone.

	ΔE_{01}	λ_{01}	f_{01}	Δq	Δr	$\Delta\mu_{01}$
n-octane						
1a	2.757	450	0.046	0.605	0.951	2.764
2a	2.462	504	0.782	0.702	3.044	10.258
3a	2.453	505	1.271	0.635	3.484	10.633
1b	2.746	452	0.045	0.612	1.037	3.047
2b	2.442	508	0.809	0.720	3.046	10.537
3b	2.435	509	1.320	0.648	3.516	10.942
1c	2.763	449	0.046	0.604	0.786	2.277
2c	2.767	448	0.556	0.653	2.373	7.438
3c	2.717	456	0.939	0.601	2.603	7.516
acetone						
1a	2.685	462	0.066	0.614	1.212	3.576
2a	2.181	568	1.038	0.742	3.485	12.411
3a	2.153	576	1.578	0.687	3.971	13.107
1b	2.674	464	0.064	0.622	1.371	4.093
2b	2.171	571	1.063	0.754	3.459	12.527
3b	2.142	579	1.609	0.698	3.955	13.260
1c	2.695	460	0.067	0.610	0.984	2.884
2c	2.598	477	0.772	0.687	2.875	9.490
3c	2.536	489	1.206	0.638	3.239	9.932

eV in acetone) the maximum absorption band and reduces its intensity, as a consequence of the lowering of the π -electron conjugation, also reflected by the increase of the BLA (Table 1).

As shown in Table 2 and S7-S11, the weakly absorbing lowest-energy $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition of SP derivatives, centered at 450 nm in n-octane, is dominated by an electronic excitation from the HOMO-1 to the LUMO, those two orbitals being mainly localized on the accepting fluorenyl moiety (Figure S2). On the other hand, the main absorption band of MC forms is associated to a HOMO-LUMO excitation. The shape of these two MOs reveals a significant intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) from the electron-donating R-phenyl group to the fluorenyl and 1,3-indandionyl moieties. Figure 3 further illustrates the electron density variation from the ground to the S_1 excited state for the three forms of compound **a**, defined as $\Delta\rho = \rho_{S_1} - \rho_{S_0} = \Delta\rho^+ + \Delta\rho^-$, with $\Delta\rho^+$ ($\Delta\rho^-$) the areas where the density increases (decreases). The photo-induced charge transfer in the SP form is clearly localized on the fluorenyl moiety, whereas it extends throughout the molecule in the MC forms.

Fig. 3 Electron density difference maps calculated in acetone for compounds **1a** (left), **2a** (center) and **3a** (right). Dark (light) blue lobes are associated with negative (positive) $\Delta\rho$ values.

The light-induced ICT can be quantified by the dipole moment variation between the S_0 and S_1 states, which can be further de-

composed as the product of the photo-induced charge displacement (Δq) and charge transfer distance (Δr): $\Delta\mu_{01} = \Delta q \times \Delta r$. As expected owing to the large increase of electron delocalisation, $\Delta\mu_{01}$ is 3-4 times larger for the MC than for the SP forms, which results from the large increase of the charge transfer distance Δr (Table 2). Δr and $\Delta\mu_{01}$ also increase slightly upon $Z \rightarrow E$ isomerization, the (Z,E) form being overall more conjugated than the (E,E) form, as mentioned above. Besides, $\Delta\mu_{01}$ presents a little increase from compound **3a** to **3b**, while it is $\sim 30\%$ smaller for **3c** consistently with the reduction of the donor strength of the R substituent.

3.3 Nonlinear optical properties

The static and dynamic second-order nonlinear responses calculated in n-octane and acetone for the three derivatives are summarized in Table 3. NLO properties calculated in other solvents are gathered in Tables S12-S16. The reported quantities include the total HRS hyperpolarizabilities (β_{HRS}), the associated depolarization (DR), and the NLO contrasts with respect to the SP form, defined as $\eta = \beta_{HRS}^{MC}/\beta_{HRS}^{SP}$.

Table 3 Static ($\lambda = \infty$) and dynamic ($\lambda = 1907$ nm) HRS first hyperpolarizability (β_{HRS} , a.u.) and depolarization ratio (DR), as well as hyperpolarizability contrasts with respect to the SP form (η), as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in n-octane and acetone.

	Static			Dynamic		
	β_{HRS}	DR	η	β_{HRS}	DR	η
n-octane						
1a	627	5.82	/	678	6.19	/
2a	13115	5.42	20.91	20163	5.37	29.72
3a	21918	4.79	34.94	34166	4.87	50.36
1b	679	5.19	/	734	5.55	/
2b	14236	5.39	20.95	22060	5.34	30.06
3b	23698	4.79	34.88	37229	4.88	50.73
1c	439	6.46	/	473	6.60	/
2c	5532	5.55	12.59	7685	5.49	16.26
3c	10650	4.64	24.24	15032	4.73	31.80
acetone						
1a	1168	6.23	/	769	6.32	/
2a	29472	5.51	25.24	24578	5.41	31.98
3a	47404	4.79	40.60	40361	4.88	52.52
1b	1236	6.04	/	830	5.87	/
2b	30897	5.49	25.00	26940	5.37	32.45
3b	49489	4.79	40.04	43923	4.89	52.91
1c	889	6.77	/	544	6.58	/
2c	10649	5.66	11.97	8706	5.53	16.00
3c	18897	4.58	21.25	16019	4.72	29.44

As observed for all derivatives, the increase of π -electron conjugation associated with the breaking of the spiro junction strongly enhances the HRS response. In n-octane, the **1a** \rightarrow **2a** isomerization is accompanied by a variation of the static β_{HRS} of ~ 21 . The MC(E,E)/SP NLO contrast increases further to ~ 30 when considering the dynamic responses, owing to stronger frequency dispersion effects on the HRS hyperpolarizability of the MC form. The **2a** \rightarrow **3a** Z/E isomerization also induces a large increase ($+70\%$) of β_{HRS} , so that the static (dynamic) NLO response of **3a** is ~ 35 (~ 50) times larger than that of the initial cyclic form. The NLO enhancement upon Z/E transformation can be qualitatively rationalized using the two-state approximation (equation 2), and mainly ascribed to the large increase of the oscillator strength

from **2a** to **3a** (Table 2).

As expected owing to their very similar absorption properties, the derivatives with R = NMe₂ and R = NEt₂ display very similar β_{HRS} responses and contrasts. Reversely, using R = OMe strongly lowers the magnitude of the first hyperpolarizability of the SP form (-30%), and even more that of the MC forms ($-50-60\%$), as a result of the large blue shift of the first absorption band. This non-symmetrical impact of chemical substitution on the relative amplitudes of β_{HRS} leads to a strong decrease of the static and dynamic β -contrasts. Finally, consistently with the lowering of the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition energies, increasing the solvent polarity from n-octane to acetone globally increases the HRS hyperpolarizability of the SP and MC forms of the three derivatives, resulting in an increased NLO contrast for derivatives **a** and **b**, while a small decrease is observed for **c** (Figure 4).

Fig. 4 Static β_{HRS} contrasts ($\eta = \beta_{HRS}^{MC}/\beta_{HRS}^{SP}$) in spirocyclohexadine derivatives, as calculated at the IEF-PCM:M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in n-octane (purple), and acetone (green).

As indicated by the DR values collected in Table 3, the NLO responses of all compounds display a dominant dipolar character. The static DR values computed in n-octane range between 4.6 and 5.8, close to the ideal value of 5.0 typical of 1D systems. DR values are nevertheless sensitive to the nature of the R substituent, as well as to geometrical changes occurring upon isomerization. Except for compound **b** in low polarity solvents (n-octane and toluene), both static and dynamic DR values decrease from the SP to the MC form and from the (E,E) to (Z,E) isomer. Besides, increasing the solvent polarity induces an increase of the static DRs, while the dynamic ones only show slight variations with solvent due to the weak differences in their optical dielectric constants.

The so-called unit sphere representation (USR)²⁵ of the first hyperpolarizability tensor (Figure 5) allows to visualize the changes in the symmetry of the second-order NLO response as a function of the molecular shape. In this representation scheme, effective induced dipoles defined as $\vec{\mu}_{eff} = \beta : \vec{F}^2(\theta, \phi)$, where β is the first hyperpolarizability tensor and $\vec{F}(\theta, \phi)$ is a unit vector of the incident electric field with polarization defined in the spherical coordinates (θ, ϕ), are plotted at each (θ, ϕ) point of the surface of a sphere centered on the center of mass of the molecules.

The USRs of the three forms highlight the 1D character of the

Fig. 5 Unit sphere representation of the static first hyperpolarizability tensors calculated in acetone for compounds **1a** (left), **2a** (center) and **3a** (right). The scale of the effective dipoles has been multiplied by 10 for the SP form (**1a**) with respect to the MC forms.

second-order NLO response typical of push-pull systems, with effective SHG dipoles oriented parallel to the charge-transfer axis. They also highlight the significant increase of the first hyperpolarizability induced by the cleavage of the spiro junction, as well as by the rotation from the *Z* to the *E* isomer.

3.4 Optimization of the NLO contrast

Electron density difference maps reported in Figure 3 reveal that the light-induced ICT in the MC forms of compounds **a-c** does not extend neither onto the phenyl ring of the 1,3-indandionyl moiety, nor on the terminal cycle of the fluorenyl. An increase of the efficiency of the π -electron conjugation, and in turn of the magnitude of the second-order NLO responses of the MC forms, might thus be achieved by grafting electron-withdrawing substituents onto those two residues. In this section, we address the NLO properties of the series of substituted derivatives schematized in Figure 6, which were designed with the aim of optimizing the NLO contrast upon photoisomerization. In particular, we consider fluorinated derivatives, which might be prepared by using 4-fluoro- or 4,7-difluoro-1H-indene-1,3(2H)-dione precursors²⁶ in the synthetic process.

Fig. 6 Substitution pattern of 1,3-indandione-derived spirocyclohexadine compounds.

Considering compound **a** as reference, fluorination at position 4 of the 1,3-indandionyl moiety (compound **d**) does not affect

Table 4 Static ($\lambda = \infty$) and dynamic ($\lambda = 1907$ nm) HRS first hyperpolarizability (β_{HRS} , a.u.) and depolarization ratio (DR), as well as hyperpolarizability contrasts with respect to the SP form (η), as calculated at the M06-2X/6-311+G(d) level in acetone for substituted derivatives shown in Figure 6.

	Static			Dynamic		
	β_{HRS}	DR	η	β_{HRS}	DR	η
1d	1164	6.13	/	765	6.26	/
3d	48749	4.76	41.89	41424	4.86	54.16
1e	1265	6.68	/	833	6.73	/
3e	48688	4.75	38.49	41407	4.86	49.68
1f	1144	5.92	/	731	5.93	/
3f	50768	4.74	44.39	42810	4.85	58.53
1g	909	5.38	/	589	5.76	/
3g	59929	4.79	65.92	52113	4.93	88.45
1h	795	5.03	/	500	5.27	/
3h	59587	4.73	74.98	51323	4.88	102.71
1i	1952	6.34	/	1453	6.57	/
3i	53404	4.86	27.36	46043	4.94	31.70
1j	3383	5.68	/	2723	5.75	/
3j	55582	4.98	16.43	48427	5.05	17.78
1k	3021	5.32	/	2407	5.41	/
3k	55378	4.90	18.33	48705	5.04	20.24
1l	2025	5.14	/	1247	5.09	/
3l	53342	4.69	26.35	47502	4.82	38.09
1m	1704	6.77	/	1039	6.58	/
3m	45102	4.62	26.47	39819	4.74	38.33
1n	1794	6.93	/	1138	6.87	/
3n	46729	4.68	26.05	40437	4.79	35.53

the first hyperpolarizability of the SP form and slightly raises that of MC (*Z,E*), resulting in $\sim 3\%$ larger static and dynamic NLO contrasts (Table 4). Reversely, fluorination at position 5 (**e**) induces a greater augmentation of the NLO response of SP, with a detrimental impact on the contrast (-5%). Positions (4,7) are thus more appropriate than (5,6) for chemical substitutions aiming at enhancing the variation of the first hyperpolarizability. Accordingly, fluorination at both 4 and 7 positions (**f**) increases the β contrast by 10%. 4,7-substitution with strong π -acceptor groups such as cyano (**g**) or nitro (**h**) further strengthens this effect, translating into an enhancement of the static NLO contrasts by up to 85%. In these two derivatives, the significant increase of the NLO response of the MC form is ascribed to the reduction of the HOMO-LUMO gap, which lowers the energy of the first absorption band by ~ 0.2 eV (Table S17). As shown in Figure S4, the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ transition is also associated to a larger delocalization of the ICT, although the $\Delta\mu_{01}$ values do not increase with respect to the reference compound. Reversely, substitution on the fluorenyl moiety (**i-j**) raises the NLO response of both SP and MC forms, to the detriment of the contrast. The same effect is obtained by simultaneously substituting the 1,3-indandionyl and fluorenyl units (**k**). Finally, extending the cycle of the 1,3-indandionyl moiety (**l-n**) is also altering the contrast, which drops by $\sim 85\%$ with respect to the reference compound.

4 Conclusion

The second-order NLO properties of spirocyclohexadine photo-switches have been evaluated by means of DFT calculations. The reported results show that the enhancement of electron conjugation occurring upon photo-isomerization from the spiro-

ran to the merocyanine form in previously reported compounds **a-c** induces variations in the first hyperpolarizability of amplitudes ranging from 30 to 50 depending on the nature of the electron-donating substituent. Such contrasts are of the same order of magnitude as those calculated for other spiroheterocyclic photochromes such as oxazine⁷ or indolino-oxazolidine derivatives,¹⁰ as well as for negative Stenhouse photochromes.¹⁸ Computationally aided chemical design further demonstrated that a significant enhancement of the NLO response of the merocyanine form, as well as of the NLO contrast, might be achieved by grafting π -electron withdrawing groups in ortho positions of the 1,3-indandionyl moiety. These results thus indicate that spirocyclohexadine derivatives behave as highly efficient NLO switches and present a real potential for integration into light-responsive NLO materials.

5 Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare.

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